

REMEMBERING DOCTOR CARLO URBANI

Revisiting a Great Italian Hero during the Covid19 Pandemia

El hombre va, en ocasiones, encuentro a su destino, ciegamente. A veces temprano, a veces tarde, en primavera o en otoño. En el medio de lo movimiento banal del Mundo y de las cosas inútiles de los días mediocres uno piensa en lo que está a punto de llegar, en la emoción desconocida y definitiva. Y el corazón que ama el combate y la aventura disfruta del pensamiento de esta crisis única cuyo final misterioso puede ser la felicidad o la muerte.

Froylan Turcios: “Encuentro fatal”. Tegucigalpa, 1905.

It was a decadent Roman fall, late afternoon of Friday November 14, 2003, when I was contacted by dr. Egidio di Pede asking me to join a pool of teachers for a training course organized by ANAAO[1] upon international medical cooperation for doctors. The title of the initiative was: *Scuola “Carlo Urbani” per la formazione dei Medici per la Cooperazione Internazionale*. At that time I was in Rome - after a short time assignment in Afghanistan with the French NGO *Aide Medicale Internationale* - attending the final phases of a one-year master on health services management by the Italian National Health Institute ISS[2]. And while to be honored for this invitation I was quite reluctant to admit that, at that time, I was not fully aware of who doctor Carlo Urbani was.

Now, 17 years after that day, during what is until now the worst airborne viral pandemic of the century, I think that the name of this great Italian doctor it is still not known enough and shall be remembered and revisited to better appreciate what he did.

Doctor Carlo Urbani was born on day October 19, 1956, in the beautiful small town of Castelplanio, province of Ancona, Italy, in a family with solid educational and religious background. His father was a teacher in the local Nautical Institute of Ancona; his mother was the headmistress of a primary school. His humanitarian drive was evident from youth: he participated as volunteer to the activities of the NGO “*Mani Tese*” and organized holydays camps for people with handicap. Beside philanthropism young Carlo also liked arts, photography, music and chants: passions and interest he kept for all his life. He used to play the organ in the local church and was a good pilot of ultralight airplanes.

Medicine as a study, profession and mission was the natural choice for a man like this. Urbani graduated in 1981 in the University of Ancona; then in 1984 he specialized in Infectious & Tropical Diseases in the University of Messina. He also earned postgraduate degrees in Tropical Parasitology and Malariology from the ISS in Roma.

In the late 1980s, he visited Mauritania several times as a volunteer to support its Ministry of Health in control of the parasitic disease Schistosomiasis.

In 1990 he was already working as *Aiuto Medico* (vice-chief department) in the *Malattie Infettive* department of the Hospital of Macerata. He had married Miss Giuliana Chiorrini in 1987 and the couple had three sons: Tommaso, Luca and Maddalena.

However, by the early 1990s it was clear to the young doctor Urbani that his future working boundaries would not had to be limited to the Hospital of Macerata. When Dr. Lorenzo Savioli - then WHO’s coordinator of parasitic diseases and vector control, based in Geneva - invited Urbani on a WHO mission in 1993 to research the epidemiology of hookworms in the Maldives, he accepted enthusiastically. But it was not the charm of tropical islands to attract Urbani. He was a curious, avid researcher: from sunrise to sunset, ignoring the beeches and crystal lagoon waters, he and Savioli worked to track down hookworms epidemiology and to train local health workers. In the evenings they were joking over their condition: “*Nobody at headquarter was going to believe we were spending our days in the Maldives over fecal samples*” Savioli told later to The New York Times[3]. But there were reasons for such Stakhanovism: Urbani was aware that in poor Countries worms does much damage but could be easily cured. A few cents pill given to a child twice a year can save his live.

The mission was an outstanding success and WHO co-opted Urbani for further missions to fight hookworms around the world. Back to Mauretania, he was the first to report transmission of *Schistosoma Mansoni* in that Country. But WHO’s assignments always were temporary. Carlo needed a more stable enrolment: in 1995 he joined the Swiss branch of *Médecins sans Frontières* (MSF) who sent him in Cambodia. Carlo decided to go there with his family: Giuliana, Tommaso and Luca (Maddalena was still to arrive later) installed themselves with him in Phnom Penh. It was, for the Italian family, an extraordinary, sometime even daring experience: in 1997 they had to witness the *coup d’etat* by the ex-khmer rouge Hun Sen to regain virtual dictatorial power in the Country. Extensively traveling “on the field” - as per the common humanitarian jargon - frequently under armed escort for the danger of the Khmer Rouge, Urbani progressively extended the MSF initiative to South East Asia: Cambodia, Vietnam and Laos. There he set up efficient measures to contain *Skistosoma Mekongi*. It is

written in his Curriculum Vitae: *“Targets of this control were usually the most disadvantaged groups of the population, and in those missions one objective was to assess the most cost-effective and sustainable interventions”*[4]. His imagination was at work to solve complicated problems. It was not possible - for example - to convince Cambodians and Laotians to give up eating undercooked fish, but teaching fish farmers to divert sewage from their ponds was an efficient alternate measure. Constantly campaigning for cheaper lifesaving drugs Dr. Urbani was a promoter of the use of *praziquantel* as anti-worms drug; he was also convincing Vietnamese farmers to grow more sweet wormwood, a plant that can produce *artemisin*, a cheap and effective anti-malaria drug.

In 1999 Dr. Carlo Urbani was appointed president of MSF, Italian branch. In such role he had to be part of the team who went to Oslo to retire the Nobel Prize for Peace assigned to MSF in that year. During the ceremony with the related acceptance and thanking speech he stated clearly one concept: *“Doctors have to stay near to their patients, near to the victims, near to the ones who need them”*. He will have to follow this statement to the very end.

It was January of the year 2000 when WHO finally enrolled Urbani for a longer mission. He had to make base in Hanoi for three years working as specialist in Malaria and Schistosomiasis for Vietnam, Laos, Cambodia and the Philippines. Giuliana was not so happy, in the beginning, to follow him there, with the little Maddalena just two months old at that time. While Tommaso and Luca studied French and attended the *Lycée Francaise de Hanoi*, little Maddalena was sent to the Vietnamese kindergarten resulting in ... the need of an interpreter at home when she started to speak!

As usual dr. Carlo went here and there on field missions to follow up on his work. *“It's possible to study an epidemic with a computer or to go to patients and see how it is in them,”* said later Dr. William Claus, the WHO group's emergency coordinator for Asia. *“Carlo was in the second category.”*

One day in Northern Vietnam, near the Border with South West China, he attended a mother and his son, both shivering with fever being affected by malaria. Then he photographed the two and after few days he showed the picture to the famous Italian photographer Nino Leto, in Vietnam for a reportage: *“You see: these are the things you need to show!”* The things went on for Leto to develop a full photographic project on this theme.

Being a *“doctor on the side of the patients”* Urbani was also a good clinician, a condition well known to his mates in Hanoi. And then it was like this than when one day in the first months of 2003 WHO-Hanoi received a call from the French-Vietnamese Hospital to the meaning of: *“Can you please send somebody consultant on a strange case of pneumonia we have here?”* the feedback was the usual one: *“Ok: call Carlo!”*.

It was Friday February 28, 2003. There are moments in the life of a man when all conspire to be crucial, life changing for one, for few, for many, sometime for millions of human beings. And this one was just one of those moments, when Dr. Carlo Urbani entered the Hanoi French-Vietnamese Hospital to visit Mr. Johnny Chen, a Chinese-American businessman. All his life had prepared this *“doctor on the side of patients”* to this very moment. All his studies, practice, experience, missions, humanitarian drive, ethic, faith and dreams were there with him. And so, shortly after having seen and visited Mr. Cheng, he was aware to be in front of something different, something still unknown and bad; actually VERY bad... and very dangerous!

“Giuliana this is not a flu” he said to this wife. Not less than 22 nurses and doctors in the French-Vietnamese hospital were already starting to develop symptoms. Urbani immediately sounded alarm to WHO-Hanoi and insisted to scale up immediately at international level. Inside the French-Vietnamese Hospital he enforced the use of Personal Protective Equipment[5]. He obtained specimens from Mr. Chen to examine them personally and sent them all over to the best virology laboratories of the World. There was natural initial resistance to accept the idea of a new, unknown and lethal virus, but Carlo had the knowledge, the authority and the freedom to crush any illogical resistance. Shortly after, first Hanoi city, then all Vietnam, went onto lockdown. The best epidemiologists and virologists of the planet jumped to Hanoi. Never before (nor after!) the WHO was able to perform such a fast response.

The contact of Mr. Chen was rapidly traced down: he had just arrived in Hanoi on February 23 coming from Shanghai, where he was to attend a symposium and where he shared a room in the Metropole Hotel on the Bund with a Mr. Liu Jianlun. This Mr. Liu was a physician at a Chinese hospital that had seen patients with a mysterious respiratory disease that first appeared among chefs and butchers working with exotic meats in the Guangdong province of Southern China.

Can't our reader feel a “*déjà vu*”? If “yes” this will increase when adding that the first cases of what will be called soon after the SARS were later traced down to November 2002: i.e. 4 months before alarm was done; and alarm was done, in Hanoi, Vietnam, by a non-Chinese health person: Dr. Carlo Urbani from Castelplanio, province of Ancona, Italy.

As result in the next few weeks first Guandong province, then all of PR China, then the majority of South West Asia went to lockdown. When the virus was insulated it was found to be a new, still unknown RNA-virus of the family of the Coronavirus and the disease it provoked was named Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome: SARS.

Then back in those first days of March 2003 Giuliana was unhappy and worried: *“With such a dangerous disease, spreading so fast, you should stay at little more at cover!” “If I can't work in such situations, what I'm here for?”* – Dr. Carlo replied -*“Answering emails, going to cocktail parties and pushing paper?”*

With all the crowd of specialists now on the field in Hanoi the exhausted Urbani was finally convinced to take a sort of rest attending a congress in Bangkok, to share the findings and actualize the colleagues on the new disease. It was March 11, 2003, few days before total lockdown. Carlo boarded an airplane in Hanoi but unfortunately during the flight he started to feel bad: fever, cough, shortness of breath. At arrival in Bangkok he immediately went to the Hospital, explained his condition and was admitted with all the necessary precautions.

Then he called Giuliana: *“I have to say you something you will not like”. “It's all ok, but do NOT tell me that you have got the disease!” “Yes, Giuliana. Now take the children and go home!”*. She sent the children to the grandfathers in Italy but decided to reach his husband in Bangkok instead. Despite aggressive treatment Urbani was rapidly progressing toward respiratory failure. Speaking five minutes a day with her husband through highly protective devices she recorded his last words: *“I'm, happy ... but very tired. I have to sleep now”*.

Urbani was a strong man, but the viral charge and his hard work had been too much. He had already asked for a priest. He also asked for his lungs to be donated in order to be studied on

the anatomico-pathology of SARS. Deeply comatose, his heart stopped to beat on the day March 29, 2003, at 11:40 local time. He was 46.

The battle was lost, but the war was won: SARS was under control. The disease created high burden in the Far East, especially in Mainland China and Hong Kong, with a little secondary cluster in Canada (many Chinese Canadians were there) but in the end, after 9 months of war, it caused just - officially - 774 deaths totally. We can now, in the middle of the SARS CoV2, understand better what all this was really: with his sacrifice Dr. Carlo Urbani contributed crucially to save millions of human lives. We as health personnel of all countries of the world, and simply as human beings, should be proud of such a man.

Giuliana returned safely in Italy; she and the children remained in quarantine as necessary but didn't develop SARS. She is now president of the local Italian Red Cross unit in Castelplanio. Tommaso follows the steps of his father and now works as manager and logistician for MSF and INTERSOS. He said: *"The last day October 19, 2020, my father would have turned 64 years old. We, his three sons and our mother, give him all our love and the proudness for what he did, for his humanitarian drive which would have been even more valuable in a time like this one, when he would have been of great help"*.

It is true. Should we had enjoyed another Carlo Urbani in Wuhan in the fall of 2019 maybe there would be NO covid-19 all over the World now.

Instead, what we had in Wuhan in the fall of 2019 was Dr. Ai Fen, the female director of the Emergency Department of the local Wuhan Central Hospital, not very far from a place called *"Huanan[6] Seafood Wholesale Market"*. Dr. Ai Fen examined a first strange case of severe *"influenza"* resistant to the therapy with radiologic image of *"multiple patchy blurry shadows scattered in lungs"* on December 18, 2019. The case referred to a delivery person of the Huanan

Seafood Market. She observed a second patient with a similar clinical condition on December 27, but this patient had no clear contact with that seafood market. However, when she received the results of the test on this second patient, in the afternoon of December 30, showing "SARS coronavirus, pseudomonas aeruginosa, 46 types of oral / respiratory colonization bacteria" she immediately reported to the hospital's public health department and infection department. She also circled the word "SARS" and sent the report to a doctor at another hospital in Wuhan. From there the report spread within local medical chat and reached Dr. Li Wenliang, an ophthalmologist in the same Wuhan Central Hospital. At 17:43 local time of this day December 30, 2019, Dr. Li Wenliang wrote his classmates on his personal blog of the Chinese "Wechat" communication service online that there were already "seven confirmed cases of SARS in the hospital, all coming from the Huanan Seafood Market". He also added a CT scan image of the lungs of a patient. At 18:42 of the same day he added that "according to the latest news it is confirmed that those are cases of coronavirus infection". Very fast the information spread largely online creating alarm in the local medical community of Wuhan. Two days later, on January 1, 2020, Dr. Ai Fen had already noticed the admission of multiple pneumonia patients by a private clinic owner located near the Huanan Market, and again warned the public health's department. She wrote: "Once emergency doctors or nurses get sick, it would be a lot of trouble."

But this time the reaction of the health authorities in Wuhan was very different compared to what happened in Hanoi 17 years before.

Dr. Ai Fen was summoned by the hospital directors and heavily criticized for spreading "false information". They named her "The Whistle Giver"[7]. To Dr. Li Wenliang, the ophthalmologist, it was reserved an even stronger treatment: on the day January 3, 2020, he was called in by the Wuhan Police ordering him to the Public Security Bureau where he was forced to sign a letter accusing him of "making false comments" that had "severely disturbed the social order" and promising to make "no further comment on this issue".[8]

Ai Fen and Li Wenliang were temporarily silenced, but Mother Nature does not care of such stupidities. On day January 10 the poor Dr. Li started coughing. On day January 11 Ms. Hu

Vital weeks were passing without any major action to stop the virus to grow from local epidemia to world pandemia. These were the same amount of vital weeks in which Dr Urbani in Hanoi was able to activate local and world authorities with the maximum efficiency back in 2003.

By Friday February 7, 2020, at 02.58 a.m. Dr. Li Wenliang - 34 years old and with his wife pregnant of their second son - was dead. He was killed by what we know now as Novel Coronavirus 2 already with, at that very time, other 636 persons all over 31,161 confirmed cases in mainland China. And now it was not anymore possible to mask the truth. But it was - as we now very painstakingly know - already too late. The virus was already circulating worldwide. On day March 11 the WHO finally declared the covid-19 to be a pandemia[10].

We shall give honor to these brave Chinese doctors. Li Wenliang payed the highest price. Ai Fen remained for 40 days inside the Emergency Department of the Wuhan Central Hospital, without rest, to fight the virus. They denounced and advised, but they were silenced. They did what was in their power and in their conscience to do but, sadly, in front of an authoritarian and secretive, auto-referential system, it was not enough. Back in 2003, with another background and in another Country, Dr. Carlo Urbani was able to make a difference ... and actually a very BIG difference.

I suggest we should now stop a moment and remember all these men and women, doctors, nurses and medical staff who courageously have put their knowledge and altruism against this merciless global plague. The exact number will never be known but as far as the end of October 2020 an estimated >20,000 of them lost their life in this fighting[11]. In PR China Dr. Ai Fen is now considered a heroine and Dr. Li Wenliang a martyr; apparently, the Chinese Government even apologized for his warning reproach. As traditional in Infectiology, Dr. Carlo Urbani is remembered by the scientific name given to the virus SARS CoV-1, or *Coronavirus Urbani* in his honor. Urbani received - *in memoriam* - the Medal of People's Health and the Medal of Friendship by the Vietnamese Government. The Italian Government awarded him the Gold Medal of Public Health (April 7, 2003) and the Cross of Great Knight of the Order of the Italian Star (May 28, 2020). To the name of Urbani are entitled many roads and squares in Italy as well as three schools and the new hospital of Jesi near Ancona.

All this is good to remember this man and his legacy, together with all the health personnel of the world engaged in this uneven struggle against suffering and avoidable deaths. Because what we need now, and will need in the next future are 10, 100, 10,000, One Million new Carlo Urbani ... and Li Weinliang ... and Ai Fen ... brave, knowledgeable and - very importantly - FREE doctors, nurses and health staff in order to prevent, identify, mitigate, stop and destroy as soon as possible any further pandemia of this sort. Something like covid-19 should never happen again. We need a new generation of "doctors to the side of the patients", we need a new Urbani generation.

Thank you for reading and spreading this paper.

Dr. Giorgio M Cortassa MD 2020, December 24. Caracas

NB: Please visit the website of AICU "Associazione Italiana Carlo Urbani" ONLUS (www.aicu.it) where you can have the opportunity to make a donation to support the humanitarian projects of the association.

Notes and References:

[1] *The Associazione Nazionale Aiuti e Assistenti Ospedalieri (ANAAO) is one of the biggest Italian syndicate of hospital's doctors.*

[2] *Istituto Superiore di Sanità.*

[3] *"Disease's Pioneer Is Mourned as a Victim; The New York Times, April 8, 2003.*

[4] *Obituary. "Carlo Urbani." The Lancet Vol. 361. April 26, 2003.*

[5] *Obituaries. "Carlo Urbani, World Health Organization official who raised the alarm over severe acute respiratory syndrome". BMJ Vol 326. April 12, 2003.*

[6] *"Hua-Nan" meaning is "Southern China".*

[7] *Internet Archives on the Wayback Machine. <https://www.hk01.com/大國小事/445884/新冠肺炎-發哨人-反被指-造謠-源頭-李文亮同事望獲道歉>*

[8] *Coronavirus kills Chinese whistleblower doctor, BBC News, February 7, 2020. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-51403795>*

[9] *"The Whistle-Giver" (发哨子的人) article in Chinese from "People" Magazine. Archived. Removed from the web by local authorities, it is still censored at time of writing (2020, December 24) <https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s/nEy0jq5wjj-g6DQVZep1Wg>*

[10] *WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19 - 11 March 2020 <https://www.who.int/director-general/speeches/detail/who-director-general-s-opening-remarks-at-the-media-briefing-on-covid-19---11-march-2020>.*

[11] *ICN confirms 1,500 nurses have died from COVID-19 in 44 countries and estimates that healthcare worker COVID-19 fatalities worldwide could be more than 20,000. 28 October 2020 <https://www.icn.ch/news/icn-confirms-1500-nurses-have-died-covid-19-44-countries-and-estimates-healthcare-worker-covid>*

Images and credit:

Page 1: Dr. Carlo Urbani at works in the Maldives Islands, circa 1993. Credit Dr. Carlo Urbani family from the AICU website.

Page 5: Dr. Ai Fen in the Wuhan Central Hospital Emergency Department. April 2020. Credit Renwu Weibo Magazine from [archive.today https://mp.weixin.qq.com](https://mp.weixin.qq.com)

Page 6: Dr. Li Wenliang in the Wuhan Central Hospital. January 2020. Credit Dr. Li Wenliang. Photo in the public domain.

Page 7: The Admonition Letter to Dr. Li Wenliang by the Police Office of Wuhan. January 3, 2020. Credit: Dr. Li Wenliang. Photo in the public domain. Translation in the next page.

**TRANSLATION OF THE ADMONITION LETTER TO DR LI WENLIANG BY THE
POLICE OF WUHAN**

Wuhan City Public Security Bureau

Wuchang Branch Zhongnan Road Street Police Station

The Letter of Admonition

With the approval of the Central Committee, the State Supervisory Committee decided to send an investigation team to Wuhan, Hubei Province, to conduct a comprehensive investigation on related issues reported by the masses involving Dr. Li Wenliang. Announcement of Wuhan Municipal Government (February 7, 2020) Text source: Caixin Report Wuhan South Public Security Bureau Wuchang Branch Zhongnan Road Street Police Station Admonition Wu Gong (Zhong) No. (20200103)

Disciplined: Li Wenliang; Sex: Male; Birthday: October 12, 1986 ID number types and numbers: (Redacted) Current address (location of residence): (Redacted), Wuhan City Workplace: Central Hospital of Wuhan

Illegal activities (time, location, participants and number of participants, problems received and consequences): Posting false statement: "7 confirmed SARS cases at Wuhan Hua'nian Fruit and Seafood Market" on the WeChat group "Wuhan University Clinical Class of 2004" on Dec 30, 2019.

[We are] now filing an official warning and admonition for the illegal action of posting false and untrue statements on the Internet in accordance with the law. Your behavior severely disrupts social order and exceeds the scope permitted by the law in addition to violating the relevant provisions of the *Public Security Administration Punishment Law of the People's Republic of China*, which makes this an illegal act! The police authority hopes that you can cooperate with our work, listen to the admonishment by the police officers and stop conducting illegal activities.

Are you able to do that? Answer: *Yes*.

We hope that you calm down and reflect carefully, and solemnly warn you: if you act stubbornly, and continue to carry out illegal activities, you will be punished by the law!

Do you understand? Answer: *Understood*.

Disciplined: *Li Wenliang* (January 3, 2020) Officers: *Hu Guifang Xu Jinhang* Police unit: Wuhan South Public Security Bureau Wuchang District Bureau Zhongnan Subdistrict Zhongnan Road police station January 3, 2019[sic]